

Batch Dilatometer for Measurement of Excess Volumes of Ternary Mixtures and Ternary Volume Effects in Benzene—Carbon tetrachloride—Cyclohexane Mixtures at 298.15 K

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A new batch dilatometer for measurement of excess volumes of ternary mixtures is described and used for the measurement of this property for 35 mixtures of benzene-carbon tetrachloride-cyclohexane at 298.15 K. Two summing methods for the binary contributions have been analysed and ternary volume effects have been calculated for these mixtures which show that mutual adjustments of the molecules become poorer.

A batch dilatometer for the direct determination of excess volume of ternary mixtures (V_i^E) has been designed and described. The apparatus is an extension of the batch dilatometer for binary mixtures introduced by Lark and Palta¹. The advantage of this dilatometer is simplicity in its operation and absence of greased stoppers. The dilatometer was tested by measuring excess volumes of a number of binary mixtures consisting of benzene-cyclohexane, which agreed very well with the results already reported from these laboratories¹. Presently the dilatometer has been used to determine V_i^E of 35 mixtures of benzene (1)-carbon tetrachloride (2)-cyclohexane (3) at 298.15 K. The results have been used to determine the ternary volume effects which may be defined as the excess volume in excess of the contributions of the compository binary mixtures. The magnitudes of ternary effects present a case study of the dilution effects caused by the addition of a component to the binary mixtures of other two components. In the system under investigation, benzene and carbon tetrachloride have specific interactions and make charge-transfer complex. The addition of cyclohexane having no specific interaction with either benzene or carbon tetrachloride is expected to cause dilution of the specific interactions. The ternary effect for a given mixture

$$\Delta V^E = V_i^E - V_{123}^E \quad (1)$$

if any may be evaluated from equation (1), where V_i^E is the experimental value of the excess volume of a ternary mixture and V_{123}^E is the corresponding value obtained by the summation of the three

compository binary contributions. Two such summing up procedures have been reported in literature.

First method is due to Nissema² in which the sum of the binary contributions V_{123}^E is given by

$$V_{123}^E(a) = \sum_{i=1}^3 x_i V_i^E \quad (2)$$

where, V_i^E is the partial molar excess volume of the i -th component in the ternary mixture which is obtained from the partial molar excess volumes of component i in the (i, j) and (i, k) binary mixtures; j and k are components next and previous to i , in the cyclic order of 1, 2, 3 (*i.e.* $j, k = 1, 2, 3$ but $k \neq j \neq 1$) and are obtained from equation (3),

$$V_i^E = \frac{x_j}{x_j + x_k} (V_i^E)_{ij} + \frac{x_k}{x_k + x_j} (V_i^E)_{ik} \quad (3)$$

where, $(V_i^E)_{ij}$ is the partial molar excess volume of i -th component in (i, j) binary mixture at mole fraction $x_i/(x_i + x_j)$ of the i -th component. The contribution V_i^E is obtained by differentiating equation (4) representing the binary data,

$$V_{ij}^E = x_i x_j [A_{ij} + B_{ij}(x_i - x_j) + C_{ij}(x_i - x_j)^2] \quad (4)$$

where, A, B and C are constants determined by least-square fitting of the experimentally determined binary V^E data.

The second method has been reported by Rastogi³ which evaluates the binary contributions

by the expression,

$$V_{123}^E(b) = \frac{1}{3}[(x_1 + x_2)V_{12}^E + (x_2 + x_3)V_{23}^E + (x_3 + x_1)V_{31}^E] \quad (5)$$

where, V_{ij}^E is the excess volume of the compository binary mixture (i, j) at the mole fraction $x_i/(x_i + x_j)$ of the i-th component in the binary mixture.

The results of the two procedures may be compared by assuming the three compository binary mixtures (1, 2) (2, 3) and (3, 1) obeying the following equations,

$$V_{12}^E = x_1 x_2 [A_{12} + B_{12}(x_1 - x_2) + \dots] \quad (6)$$

$$V_{23}^E = x_2 x_3 [A_{23} + B_{23}(x_2 - x_3) + \dots] \quad (7)$$

$$V_{31}^E = x_3 x_1 [A_{31} + B_{31}(x_3 - x_1) + \dots] \quad (8)$$

One mole of an equimolar (1, 2, 3) ternary mixture statistically contains 1/3 mole of each of compository (1, 2), (2, 3) and (3, 1) equimolar binary mixtures, and the excess volume per mole of an equimolar binary mixture (i, j) is given by

$$V_{ij}^E = \frac{1}{2} A_{ij} \quad (9)$$

consequently V_{123}^E , in terms of the binary contributions should be given as

$$V_{123}^E = \frac{1}{3}(\frac{1}{2}A_{12}) + \frac{1}{3}(\frac{1}{2}A_{23}) + \frac{1}{3}(\frac{1}{2}A_{31}) = \frac{1}{6}(A_{12} + A_{23} + A_{31}) \quad (10)$$

For an equimolar ternary mixture, both equations (2) and (5) predict the expected sum, but when any of the components is absent, equation (2) predicts correct excess volume of the then left over binary mixture, but equation (5) predicts half the required value, viz. putting $x_3 = 0$ and $x_1 = x_2 = 0.5$, equation (5) gives,

$$V_{12}^E(b) = \frac{1}{2} (0.5 + 0.5) V_{12}^E \quad (11)$$

Consequently the ternary effect, as defined by equation (12),

$$V^E(a \text{ or } b) = V_{ij}^E - V_{123}^E(a \text{ or } b) \quad (12)$$

will be different except for equimolar ternary mixture, when equation (5) is used for summing up the binary contributions. The differences will be the largest at extremal conditions. This is shown to be true for the data discussed later in the paper.

Experimental

The three solvents used were of A R. grade and were further purified by the methods described elsewhere⁷. The purity of the compounds was checked by determining their refractive indices and densities, which agreed well with the literature values. The solvents were thoroughly degassed before use. The newly designed dilatometer is illustrated in Fig 1. Two limbs A and B (capacity 3-4 ml) hold two liquids, and are connected to each other through a tube T, containing mercury (M) which keeps the components apart and unmixed. These limbs have ground glass discs D and D' with pin holes in their centre. After filling, these can be sealed with teflon caps E and E₁ and metal discs F and F₁, and clamped. The third component is filled in the bulb C, which is fused in the middle of

Fig. 1. The dilatometer.

the connecting tube T and carries a capillary P of uniform bore (vol/cm = 0.00578 cm³). The filling of the dilatometer and other details are the same as described for the earlier reported dilatometer for binary mixtures. The measurements were carried out at 298.15 ± 0.01 K, in a 150 lit water thermostat.

Estimation of uncertainties: The experimentally determined excess volume of a ternary mixture V_{123}^E has been evaluated from the various measurable quantities appearing in the equation (13),

$$V_{123}^E = \frac{\Delta h(w/\rho l)}{\frac{w_1}{M_1} + \frac{w_2}{M_2} + \frac{w_3}{M_3}} \quad (13)$$

where, Δh is the difference in the levels of the liquid in the capillary (Fig. 1) before and after mixing, w is the weight of the mercury thread of length l filled in the capillary during calibration, ρ its density at the temperature of calibration; w_1 , w_2 and w_3 are the weights of the three components filled in the dilatometer, and M_1 , M_2 and M_3 are the corresponding molecular weights. The equation derived for the uncertainty in V^E , caused by the uncertainty in weights of the three components (± 0.00014 g), weight of mercury (± 0.00014 g) and the length of the mercury thread (± 0.0014 cm)

is as follows,

$$dV^E = \left[\left(\frac{d\Delta h w / \rho l}{A} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta h / \rho l dw}{A} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta h (w / \rho l^2) dl}{A} \right)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{B}{A^2} \frac{dwi}{M_i} \right)^2 + C^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

where, $A = \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{w_i}{M_i}$
 $B = \Delta h w / \rho l$

where, C is the uncertainty caused due to temperature variation of ± 0.01 K, determined by finding the shift of the level in the capillary for 0.1° rise of temperature at a mean value of 298.15 K. The overall uncertainty for representative mixtures comes out to be $\pm 0.003 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Results and Discussion

The experimental excess volumes of ternary mixtures at 298.15 K, as a function of x_1 and x_2 are summarised in Table 1. The V^E data for the com-

TABLE 1—TERNARY EXCESS VOLUME (V^E) AND TERNARY EFFECTS (ΔV^E) FOR BENZENE (1)—CARBON TETRACHLORIDE (2)—CYCLOHEXANE (3) MIXTURES AT 298.15 K

x_1	x_2	V^E	$\Delta V^E(a)$	$\Delta V^E(b)$	ΔV^E (Eqn. 18)	δV^E $\times 10^4$
$\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$						
0.0551	0.6641	0.164	0.014	0.036	0.013	1
0.0564	0.5958	0.186	0.013	0.047	0.015	-2
0.0584	0.6495	0.165	0.010	0.032	0.014	-4
0.0660	0.2674	0.232	0.013	0.086	0.017	-4
0.0718	0.1982	0.236	0.015	0.095	0.015	0
0.0757	0.5407	0.213	0.023	0.053	0.021	2
0.0812	0.1207	0.235	0.011	0.100	0.012	-1
0.0828	0.5959	0.195	0.024	0.037	0.021	3
0.0943	0.5294	0.219	0.026	0.044	0.026	0
0.1982	0.0585	0.415	0.016	0.188	0.015	1
0.2069	0.0595	0.427	0.018	0.193	0.016	2
0.2078	0.0660	0.422	0.015	0.186	0.017	-2
0.2120	0.0688	0.432	0.021	0.193	0.018	3
0.2146	0.7108	0.082	0.016	-0.014	0.017	-1
0.2380	0.7131	0.067	0.016	-0.003	0.013	3
0.2396	0.7173	0.055	0.009	-0.008	0.011	-2
0.2402	0.6915	0.086	0.021	-0.005	0.017	4
0.4023	0.5279	0.115	0.031	0.017	0.017	4
0.4192	0.0722	0.569	0.031	0.248	0.031	0
0.4266	0.4944	0.125	0.029	0.016	0.031	-2
0.4491	0.4614	0.144	0.035	0.023	0.036	-1
0.5630	0.3081	0.223	0.048	0.059	0.047	0
0.6331	0.0750	0.484	0.033	0.209	0.032	1
0.6705	0.1982	0.245	0.035	0.080	0.041	-6
0.6874	0.2753	0.082	0.013	0.026	0.017	-4
0.6880	0.2516	0.133	0.027	0.046	0.025	2
0.6995	0.2793	0.051	0.009	0.017	0.010	-1
0.7044	0.2596	0.080	0.012	0.025	0.016	-4
0.7403	0.2144	0.100	0.014	0.033	0.018	-4
0.7521	0.0989	0.299	0.030	0.122	0.028	2
0.7694	0.0476	0.368	0.023	0.169	0.017	6
0.7823	0.0454	0.352	0.021	0.162	0.016	5
0.7861	0.0519	0.333	0.022	0.151	0.017	5
0.7933	0.1618	0.101	0.011	0.035	0.015	-4
0.8111	0.0644	0.263	0.018	0.113	0.017	1

pository binary mixtures as represented by equations (15-17) were taken from literature^{1,4,5}.

$$V_{12}^E = x_1 x_2 [0.021468 - 0.024701 (x_1 - x_2) + 0.02637 (x_1 - x_2)^2] \quad (15)$$

$$V_{23}^E = x_2 x_3 [0.65809 - 0.00659 (x_2 - x_3) + 0.0279 (x_3 - x_1)^2] \quad (16)$$

$$V_{31}^E = x_3 x_1 [2.5887 - 0.1195 (x_3 - x_1) + 0.0044 (x_3 - x_1)^2] \quad (17)$$

The ternary effects $\Delta V^E(a)$ and $\Delta V^E(b)$ as defined by equation (12) were calculated, and have been included in Table 1 (columns 4 and 5). $\Delta V^E(a)$ values which represent the real ternary effects have been fitted by the method of least-squares to the equation,

$$\Delta V^E(a) = x_1 x_2 x_3 [1.800 + 1.102 (x_1 - x_2) + 0.358 (x_3 - x_1)] \quad (18)$$

The deviations of the $\Delta V^E(a)$'s from the recalculated values have been included in Table 1 (column 7). These deviations have standard mean value of $\pm 0.003 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which is of the order of estimated uncertainties in ternary volumes. The ternary effects are much larger than the individual deviations from the recalculated values and are thus much significant.

From the comparison of data in columns 4 and 5 (Table 1) it is found that ΔV^E values as predicted by equation (2) are all positive, whereas equation (5) predicts some negative values too. This may be ascribed to the failure of equation (5) to yield correct summation of binary contributions which is expected to give large deviations near extremal concentrations (small concentration of one of the components). Also, the positive $\Delta V^E(b)$ values are sometimes 10 times as large as $\Delta V^E(a)$ values. The real ternary effects $\Delta V^E(a)$ vary from 5 to 25% of the corresponding V_{ij}^E values. As all the ΔV^E values are positive, the mutual interactions of any compository binary mixture are weakened by the presence of the third component. To understand the mutual dilution effects in different mixtures

Fig. 2. Ternary effect $\Delta V^E(a)$ ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) as a function of composition; $\Delta V^E(a)$ values shown on the contours.

equivolume contours have been drawn on an equilateral triangle (Fig. 2). The three sides of the triangle represent three mole fractions. Such contours for selected values of $\Delta V^E(a)$ and x_1 were obtained through solution of equation (18) using numerical methods. It is apparent from Fig. 2 that $\Delta V^E(a)$ is maximum for mole fractions 0.40, 0.29 and 0.31 of the respective 1, 2, 3 components. When to such a mixture any one of the three components is added, the ternary effect is reduced.

The positive ternary effect, no doubt, is indicative of the reduced mutual interactions of the ternary mixtures, but this does not indicate the approach to ideal behaviour, as the condition of zero excess volume is disobeyed more and more. It may be said that in the present system studied, the mutual geometrical adjustments between the three kinds of molecules become poorer. V_i^E for eight such mixtures at 303.15 K have also been reported

earlier⁶. These values when compared with the corresponding V_i^E values at 298.15 K from the present data are found to be consistently slightly higher, the $\Delta V_i^E(a)$ values calculated for these eight mixtures showed that these vary from about 15 to 30% of the corresponding V_i^E values.

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